

Electric Dipole Moment of Benzyl mercaptan and Molecular Interaction

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The electric dipole moment of Benzyl mercaptan has been determined at 30° in two nonpolar solvents *viz.* benzene and dioxane. Our data in both the solvents are new as no one appears to have studied the dielectric polarisation of Benzyl mercaptan earlier¹. In previous communications^{2,3}, we have already shown the merits of Palit equation. It is observed that the moment value (μ_s) obtained by this equation is fairly comparable with those calculated by the methods due to Guggenheim⁴ and Halverstadt and Kumler⁵ usually employed by the workers. The molecular polarisation data in dioxane indicate that the probability of formation of charge transfer type complexes is better indicated than dipole association in the solution.

A survey of the literature reveals that only a few workers^{6,7} have determined the dielectric polarisation of alkane thiols, either to examine the equations derived from current theories of dielectric-polarisation or to study the effect of sulphur replacing oxygen in an alcoholic group. It appears from the literature¹ that the dielectric polarisation of this aromatic thiol has not been measured by earlier workers.

Experimental

The practical work essentially involves the measurement of dielectric constant, density, and refractive index of various solutions containing different mole fraction of the solute. The dielectric constant has been determined at 30° at a radio frequency of 1 Mc/sec with the help of an apparatus (Dipole meter) supplied by M/s, Toshniwal Brothers, New Delhi (India). The instrument works on the principle of heterodyne beat method. The resulting beat frequency is projected on the screen of a cathode ray tube with a 50 cycles per second horizontal deflector. A Lissajous figure is obtained on the screen. The reading for the capacitance contributed by the specimen liquid is taken at the appearance of a single loop pattern on the cathode ray tube. The reading leads to determination of dielectric constant of the liquid. The values of dielectric constants agree within ± 0.001 unit with the literature⁹ while the cell was calibrated with the standard liquids benzene, cyclohexane, carbon tetrachloride and dioxane.

Purification : Benzyl mercaptan (Evans Chemetics, Inc., New York) was purified before use by distilling over anhydrous sodium sulphate in a quick-fit apparatus where there was no possibility for the liquid to be in contact with atmospheric moisture or carbon dioxide. Benzene (Sarabhai Merck Ltd., G. R.) and dioxane (B. D. H., A. R. reagent) were used as such after checking the dielectric constant values of these liquids with the literature⁹ values.

Results and Discussion

The experimental data are reported in the Tables 1 to 6. From the data in table 6 it is apparent that the moment value in both the solvents by all the three methods are fairly consistent. Further to ascertain the reliability of the data the values obtained have been compared with those available in the literature^{10,11} for Benzyl alcohol in benzene and dioxane. It is assumed that Benzyl mercaptan is derived from

Fig. 1 Benzyl Mercaptan in Dioxane

The present work has therefore been undertaken to determine the dipole moment value of this compound and to ascertain the accuracy in the results obtained. Besides, the molecular polarisation data have been utilized in understanding the applicability of Earp and Glasstone⁸ theory to study the molecular interaction in a binary mixture.

Benzyl alcohol replacing oxygen by sulphur, a less electronegative atom. Consequently, it is believed that the moment value for Benzyl mercaptan should be less than that of Benzyl alcohol. In both the solvents our observed values are considerably lower than those of Benzyl alcohol and as such the data support the above view. However, the order of moment remains the same i. e. the value in dioxane is greater than that in benzene.

Benzyl mercaptan in Benzene

S. No.	$\epsilon_1=2.2635$ m_1	$d_1=0.8676$ m_2	$n_1=1.4950$ f_2	v_{12}	ϵ_{12}
1	17.2286	0.2833	0.0102	1.1491	2.2892
2	17.1947	0.6044	0.0216	1.1458	2.3188
3	17.1502	0.8392	0.0299	1.1425	2.3353
4	17.2085	1.1089	0.0389	1.1398	2.3764
5	17.2517	1.3876	0.0481	1.1374	2.3993
6	17.2245	1.6342	0.0563	1.1351	2.4175
7	17.1156	1.9375	0.0665	1.1321	2.4426

Values of the constants in the equation of Halverstadt and Kumler.

$$\alpha=2.8171 \quad \epsilon_1=2.2585 \quad P_{2\alpha}=77.26 \text{ ml}$$

$$\beta=0.3005 \quad d_1=1.1518 \quad \mu=1.38 \text{ D.}$$

TABLE 2

S. No.	$\omega_2 \times 10^8$	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	n_{12}	$(\epsilon_{12} - n_{12}^2)$	$C \times 10^5$
1.	16.18	2.2892	0.8702	1.4960	0.0512	11.30
2.	33.96	2.3188	0.8727	1.4970	0.0778	23.86
3.	46.65	2.3353	0.8753	1.4980	0.0913	32.86
4.	60.54	2.3764	0.8773	1.4990	0.1294	42.74
5.	74.45	2.3993	0.8792	1.5000	0.1493	52.67
6.	86.65	2.4175	0.8810	1.5010	0.1645	61.46
7.	101.69	2.4426	0.8833	1.5020	0.1866	72.29

$$\alpha_0=1.7647 \quad \epsilon_1=2.2650 \quad (\Delta/C)_0=2.285 \times 10^2$$

$$\beta_0=0.1500 \quad d_1=0.8680 \quad \mu(\text{Guggenheim})=1.37 \text{ D}$$

$$\gamma_0=0.0697 \quad n_1=1.4949 \quad \mu(\text{Palit})=1.36 \text{ D}$$

$$P_{2\mu}=37.24 \text{ c.c.}$$

Benzyl mercaptan in Dioxan

TABLE 3

S. No.	$\epsilon_1=2.2020$ m_1	$d_1=1.0215$ m_2	$n_1=1.4180$ f_2	v_{12}	ϵ_{12}
1.	20.1425	0.2983	0.0104	0.9782	2.2407
2.	20.1783	0.5768	0.0199	0.9781	2.2715
3.	20.2216	0.8653	0.0295	0.9779	2.3040
4.	20.1751	1.1527	0.0390	0.9769	2.3337
5.	20.1408	1.9901	0.0655	0.9761	2.4147

Values of the constants in the equation of Halverstadt and Kumler.

$$\alpha=3.0911 \quad \epsilon_1=2.2102 \quad P_{2\alpha}=79.02 \text{ c.c.}$$

$$\beta=-0.0408 \quad v_1=0.9787 \quad \mu=1.41 \text{ D}$$

TABLE 4

S. No.	$w_2 \times 10^8$	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	n_{12}	$(\epsilon_{12} - n_{12}^2)$	$C \times 10^5$
1.	14.59	2.2407	1.0223	1.4200	0.2243	12.01
2.	27.79	2.2715	1.0223	1.4220	0.2494	22.89
3.	41.04	2.3040	1.0226	1.4240	0.2762	33.80
4.	54.05	2.3337	1.0237	1.4265	0.2988	44.53
5.	89.92	2.4147	1.0245	1.4315	0.3655	74.15

$$\alpha_0=2.2069 \quad \epsilon_1=2.2100 \quad (\Delta/C)_0=2.260 \times 10^2$$

$$\beta_0=0.0250 \quad d_1=1.0219 \quad \mu(\text{Guggenheim})=1.41 \text{ D}$$

$$\gamma_0=0.1533 \quad n_1=1.4177 \quad \mu(\text{Palit})=1.40 \text{ D}$$

$$P_{2\mu}=39.76 \text{ c.c.}$$

TABLE 5

(1) $f_1 f_2$	(2) Solution— Polarisation P_{12}	(3) Total Polarisation of the solution $P_{12}=P_1 f_1 + P_2 f_2$	(4) Excess— Polarisation, PE (2)-(3)
0.0103	25.324	25.231	+0.093
0.0195	25.867	25.616	+0.251
0.0286	26.423	26.006	+0.417
0.0374	26.909	26.392	+0.517
0.0612	28.3 01	27.472	+0.829

TABLE 6—DIPOLE MOMENT OF BENZYL MERCAPTAN

Literature value	Benzyl mercaptan		Benzyl alcohol	
	Benzene	Dioxane	Benzene	Dioxane
Halverstadt and Kumlar method	1.38	1.41	—	—
Guggenheim method	1.37	1.41	—	—
Palit method	1.36	1.40	—	—

In the absenc of vapour moment value it was not possible to make a direct comparison. However, on extending the suggestion of Higasi^{1,2} and the discussion^{1,3} carried out in the light of his theory a positive solvent effect may safely be predicted in this case. A slightly higher value in dioxane contrary to the expectation is presumably therefore due to the formation of contact pairs complexes. To confirm this view, the theory of Earp and Glasstone⁸ has been employed and accordingly the variation of excess polarisation P^E with $f_1 f_2$ has been studied. It is observed that the curve being linear passes through origin (Figure 1). This confirms that contact pairs are exclusively formed in dioxane. The possibility of dipole-association appears to be remote as the excess polarisation values are positive.

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